

NEGATIVE EFFECTS ON THE ENVIRONMENT WHEN BURNING FUEL IN HEAT SOURCES

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The proposed article is devoted to the issues of the release of harmful emissions into the atmosphere during the combustion of various types of fuels in heat sources and their harmful effects of the Earth's ozone layer, flora and fauna.

Keywords: fuels, gas, oil, coal, harmful emissions, thermal power plant, thermal power centers, soot, oxides, thermal energy consumption, ecology.

There is an inextricable relationship and interdependence of the conditions for ensuring heat and energy consumption and environmental pollution. The interaction of these two factors of human activity and the development of production forces attracts gradual attention to the problem of the interaction of thermal energy and the environment.

At an early stage of the development of thermal power engineering, the main manifestation of this attention was the search in the environment for resources necessary to ensure heat and energy consumption and stable heat supply to enterprises and residential buildings. In the future, the boundaries of the problem covered the possibilities of more complete use of natural resources through the exploration and rationalization of processes and technology, extraction and enrichment, processing and combustion of fuel, as well as the improvement of thermal power plants.

With the growth of unit capacities of blocks, thermal power plants and thermal power systems, specific and total levels of heat and energy consumption, the task arose of limiting polluting emissions into air and water basins, as well as more complete use of their natural dissipation capacity.

At the present stage, the problem of interaction between thermal energy and the environment has acquired new features, spreading its influence over vast territories, most rivers and lakes, huge volumes of the Earth's atmosphere and hydrosphere.

The intensive development of energy, industry and transport inevitably causes an increase in the consumption of hydrocarbon fuels, which, in turn, increases the amount of its combustion products released into the atmosphere.

According to long-term monitoring, the amount of environmentally harmful chemical compounds, substances and elements of fuel combustion products released into the atmosphere doubles every 12-14 years, and therefore the problem of atmospheric pollution by fuel combustion products belongs to one of the global problems of our time.

Atmospheric pollution occurs due to imperfections in the design of equipment, engine systems and installations, violations of operating rules, low technical culture and environmental illiteracy of maintenance personnel, and sometimes as a result of accidents or emergencies.

The toxicity of flue exhaust, exhaust and exhaust gases released into the surrounding air depends mainly on the quality, grade and type of hydrocarbon fuel burned, the conditions of the organization of its combustion process, the technical condition of heat engines and fuel combustion plants.

For example, the use of low-grade fuels, on the one hand, helps to reduce the current operating costs of purchasing fuel, and on the other hand, increases the amount of environmentally hazardous pollutants released into the atmosphere.

The intensity of atmospheric pollution with harmful gases is determined by the concentration and number of pollution sources per unit area; the type, capacity and mode of use of fuel combustion plants and heat engines; the design and condition of their fuel systems, the condition and level of operation of technical means; the availability of systems and devices that qualitatively and quantitatively reduce harmful emissions into the atmosphere, and other factors.

Studies of flue exhaust gases of fuel combustion plants show that in their composition the main pollutants of atmospheric air are carbon oxides (up to 50%), sulfur oxides (up to 20 percent), nitrogen oxides (up to 6-8%), hydrocarbons (up to 5-20%), soot, oxides and derivatives of mineral inclusions and impurities of hydrocarbon fuels.

The greatest air pollution comes from installations running on hydrocarbon fuels (gasoline, kerosene, diesel fuel, fuel oil, coal, natural gas, etc.). The amount of pollution is determined by the composition, the object of the fuel burned and the organization of the combustion process. In recent years, the amount of emissions from transport accounts for about 70% of all emissions into the atmosphere.

The combustible substance of fuels consists mainly of 3 elements: C, H, S. Gorenje - rapid connection of oxygen with these combustible elements, accompanied by the release of heat.

There are three types of fuel: solid, liquid, and gaseous.

The main solid fuel is coal. The characteristics of coal vary from deposit to deposit. Coal is divided into classes and groups according to the established carbon content and the heat of combustion attributed to the mass without mineral impurities. Solid fuels include oil shale, anthracite shale, wood, products of its processing, solid waste.

Liquid fuels include refined petroleum products, coal tar, shale oils and industrial waste of various compositions. Liquid fuels are sprayed into small droplets to increase the surface available for interaction with oxygen. These droplets easily evaporate at the temperature of the furnace and are in a gaseous state during gorenje.

Gaseous fuels are easily mixed with air and do not require preparation. Natural gas, mainly methane, is the predominant gaseous fuel currently in use.

Other gaseous fuels are petroleum gases, blast furnace gas, acetylene, hydrogen and satellite gases, the composition of which depends on the type of production.

During the operation of boiler equipment, various harmful compounds enter the environment, which have a negative impact. These include:

- Gases are the main source of emissions of harmful substances into the environment. During the operation of boilers, compounds of carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide, sulfur oxide, and nitrogen enter the air.
- At large thermal power plants, liquid compounds are released, which enter the sewer system and local reservoirs.
- Emissions include soot, ash and unburned coal particles remaining after the use of solid fuels.

The most popular fuels are coal, gas and fuel oil. Each of them has its advantages and disadvantages.

- Fuel oil allows you to get the maximum amount of energy, so the amount of fuel used is significantly less. In addition, it is not explosive, and is relatively safe to use. However, fuel oil cannot be considered as an environmentally friendly fuel. When it is burned, a huge amount of harmful substances is released into the air, so today most cities purposefully refuse to use this type of fuel in favor of other energy resources.

- Natural gas attracts with its cheapness, ease of transportation and great energy potential. However, this fuel is extremely explosive, and any malfunction of the equipment can lead to a serious accident.

- Coal is the most economical type of fuel in most regions of Russia. Its environmental friendliness is also attractive – compared to other energy resources, it turns out to be the cleanest and most efficient source of heat and energy.

The largest amount of gross emissions among the city's energy sources is emissions from thermal power plants. This fact is explained by the fact that a larger number of consumers in the city are supplied with heat from the CHP (heat and electric central). But for a number of some pollutants (soot and CO), boiler houses emit more than CHP plants. This is due, among other things, to different coal burning technologies.

"Flue gas purification (for solids – soot, benzene (a)pyrene, inorganic dust) is carried out at the CHP plant more effectively. This is explained by the use of more advanced exhaust gas purification systems (a significant part of CHP emissions is cleaned in electric filters, which are much more efficient than cyclones and battery cyclones). Also, lower emission values for solids are associated with more efficient and complete combustion of fuel at a thermal power plant," the city's Heat Supply Scheme says. – Despite the fact that the load of consumers connected to boiler houses is less than 30% of the total heat load of consumers in the city, gross emissions of inorganic dust (a substance for which the maximum permissible concentration is observed in the atmosphere of the city) account for about 40% of the gross emissions of energy sources in the city."

In conclusion, it can be noted that the operation of thermal power plants (thermal power plants) also causes irreparable damage to public health, since when burning coal they emit especially dangerous volatile compounds of mercury, arsenic, selenium, lead, cadmium, zinc and others. Once in the human body, they accumulate in organs, leading to the development of malignant tumors and mutagenic effects, reducing resistance to infections. The smallest particles with a diameter of up to 0.1 microns can penetrate into the capillaries even through the skin. The distance to which ash particles are carried and their deposition to the ground together with atmospheric precipitation depends on the physical properties of the ash and weather conditions. People living at a distance of 1-2 km from the thermal power plant are most affected.

The steady increase in the intake of toxic substances into the environment primarily affects the health of the Earth's population, worsens the quality of agricultural products, reduces yields, affects the climatic conditions of certain regions of the world, the state of the Earth's ozone layer, leads to the death of flora and fauna.

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